

THE IMPORTANCE OF DEVELOPING MORAL CHARACTERS IN CHILDREN THROUGH FAMILIARITY WITH ANIMAL WORLD.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10641149>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 03st February 2024

Accepted: 05th February 2024

Published: 09th February 2024

KEYWORDS

social efficiency, standard of education, continuous education, intellectual knowledge, personality education;

ABSTRACT

In the years of independence, the educational system and education of a competent generation in the republic became the main priorities of the state policy. Improving the activities of pre-school education organizations serves as a basis for the effectiveness of activities in this field of education. According to the Decree No. PF-5198 dated September 30 , 2017 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh . Mirziyoy , preschool education is the primary link of the continuous education system. Being considered as a child, it is very important in raising a healthy and well-rounded child and preparing him for school.

concept of development of the preschool education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 (hereinafter - the Concept) of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on September 30 , 2018 "On measures to improve the management of the preschool education system" No. PQ-3955 was developed in order to implement the decision, and complex measures for the development of the preschool education system until 2030 includes. The decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan to approve the concept of development of the preschool education system until 2030 was adopted .

With high spiritual culture and high moral qualities is especially important today, when reforms in the political, economic, civil and spiritual and cultural spheres are being rapidly implemented. In -the Republic of Uzbekistan, during the years of independence, improvement of the continuous education system , providing education to the individual at the level of world education standards and increasing social efficiency were identified as one of the priority directions of the state policy . The need to improve the morale of the society requires the improvement of the education system.

Everyone knows that the year of " Healthy Child" has been declared in our country. We want not only the healthy physical and spiritual growth of our children , but also that they

become harmoniously developed people with the most modern intellectual knowledge and fully meet the requirements of the 21st century. We have set ourselves the goal of creating all the necessary opportunities and conditions for the generation to grow up. The State program adopted by our government on this issue in these days envisages the mobilization of all available resources and opportunities, taking into account the total state and non-state resources, in order to achieve this noble goal.

Education is a product of consciousness, but at the same time it is the most important factor that determines the level of consciousness and its development, that is, it forms and enriches the people's spirituality. Therefore, it is impossible to develop spirituality without changing the educational system and, on this basis, changing the consciousness.

Education cannot be separated from education, and education cannot be separated from education - this is an oriental view, an oriental philosophy of life.

Personal education is a complicated process. It requires several important factors for its implementation. The correct and creative approach to the education system, the continuity of education, the equal responsibility of society members for education, the basis of education on personal example, the priority of family education.

Theoretical features of developing children's moral qualities by introducing them to the animal world

Morality is manifested in the system of behavioral rules that regulate the behavior of people to each other, to society, to the state, to public property, to the family.

Morality exists as a person's inner world, beliefs, and qualities, while etiquette is manifested in a person's visible manners, behavior, and behavior.

In the work of the ancient philosophers and sages, moral issues have occupied a central place. They called morality the "foundation" of society. Therefore, the behavior of each member of the society is paid special attention.

All aspects of human ethics are expressed in the Holy Qur'an and the hadiths of our prophet Muhammad Alaihissalam.

We can cite the following hadiths as examples:

" In addition to honoring your children, improve their morals ", " I was sent to improve all good morals ", " A believer should not have the following two qualities: avarice and immorality ". It is known that our forefathers considered knowledge, education and training to be priceless wealth and the most important condition for human perfection and development of the nation. Of course, "education is a product of consciousness, but at the same time it is the most important factor that determines the level of consciousness and its development, that is, it enriches the spirituality of the people."

Among the monuments that express the life experience, religious, moral, scientific and literary views of our ancestors, the book "Avesta" has a special place in the priceless spiritual monument created in the territory of the Khorezm oasis. Such immortal monuments testify to the existence of a great culture in this ancient land, in the land where we live today.

If we take the principle of "Good thought, good word, good deed" that determines the basic meaning of "Avesta", then it is a lesson for the present time.

one can see that there are moral lessons to be learned. It is known that every nation has its legendary heroes and wrestlers. In this sense, the epic "Alpomish", which is a unique masterpiece of folk art, is a symbol of our nation.

It is a heroic song that shows its identity and is passed down from generation to generation. In this classic work, it has survived the storms of history, life and death tests and preserved its identity, the tolerance, perseverance, nobility of our country

moral qualities such as faithfulness and loyalty are expressed. Therefore, the epic "Alpomish" teaches us about the virtues of patriotism.

The science of pedagogy considers upbringing and education as an important factor in the moral development of the young generation. According to the results of research on pedagogy and psychology, the period of preschool education is the most important stage in the spiritual formation of a child. During this period, under the influence of education aimed at a certain goal, the moral qualities of a person begin to form. At the age of 6-7, a more stable form of positive behavior norms occurs. The child acts based on the moral norms acquired in his relations with others. Therefore, it is important to give moral education to children from an early age.

Not everyone knows that there are more than two million species of animals in the world. Interestingly, they can be found everywhere on the Earth: on the ground, in the soil, in the sea, rivers, lakes and even in the air. Animals are very important in nature and human life. Most of the food products and clothing necessary for human existence and living, as well as some raw materials needed for industry, are obtained from animals. In addition, the contribution of animals in processes such as the reproduction and spread of plants on Earth, improvement of soil composition, increase in fertility, and water purification is incomparable. For this reason, great importance is attached to the protection of animals, their preservation and breeding all over the world. In order to protect animals, first of all, it is necessary to know how to take care of them, learn what they eat, observe their behavior, and read many books about them. In this book, we have tried to give interesting information about some species of the animal world, their representatives, lifestyles and specific characteristics. O'yinchi, bu kitob sizning doimiy hamrohingiz bo'lib, sizning hayotingizdagi hayvonotni o'rganish uchun sizning doimiy hamrohingiz bo'lib, sizning hayotingizdagi hayvonotni o'rganish uchun

children knowledge about the animal world; raising moral qualities in them by instilling love for animals and living nature;

To give an understanding of the animal world, to describe them, to explain a conscious and ethical attitude towards the animal world.

held in the form of a collective group, uses the methods of presentation, conversation, question-and-answer, "Cluster" technology. Distributed material, picture cards with pictures of animals are the main means of organizing the activity, and the educator monitors the active participation of each child. The method of asking questions about the lesson also encourages children to be active and serves to concentrate their attention. Encouragement after the lesson naturally increases children's interest in future activities. Wild animals, domestic animals, birds, poultry.

Educator: - We will learn their types and differences by carefully looking at the pictures. Tell me, which animals are wild, wild, and which are called domestic animals? What are the pros and cons of these?

Pupils begin to tell their names, characteristics and harmful aspects as much as they know.

shows pictures of different animals and divides them into classes together with the children (classification); that is, they separate pictures of domestic animals, wild animals, poultry, and birds.

Stage III. At this stage, the educator divides the children into groups, offering them to choose the animal pictures they like .

Stage IV The educator summarizes the knowledge acquired by the children.

Educator: - Children, what poems and fairy tales do you know about animals? How do you feel about these animals?

- How to care for animals? Can they suffer?
- How to protect the animal world?
- What is the importance of animals in human life?

Children find answers to questions based on the knowledge they have learned . Whichever group actively participates, flags will be distributed to that group and other group participants will be encouraged.

Children's level of mastery of knowledge, skills and abilities, moral and conscious attitudes towards the animal world are determined through conversation, problem questions, tests, and observations.

Based on the results of the experiment, children's literacy level is divided into three categories and evaluated within the problem.

1. High.
2. Medium.
3. Low.

teaches children to classify the animal world .

In the process of organizing the moral education of preschool children, determining the optimal forms, methods and tools of activities aimed at using the animal world will not only serve to create the possibility of effectively organizing practical activities on the research problem in the future, raising it to higher levels, but at the same time forming the skills of organizing activities, as well as helps them to fully understand the essence of the animal world, which expresses moral ideas in its content. Through activities , children's thinking, reasoning and understanding of plants and animals will increase.

According to scientists, human life in the 21st century depends crucially on "the field of education, the direction and effectiveness of teaching and educating the young generation, their intellectual and moral qualities." Preschool childhood as a period of human life plays a special role in the formation of not only every person, but also the entire humanity, the whole world. Educational, ideological, moral, cultural and physical priorities of preschool childhood determine the life paths of generations, affect the development and state of the entire civilization. Now it is necessary to pay as much attention as possible to the formation of the inner world of the child, to the upbringing of the creative principle in him . Reading is a special type of value in this matter, because in the process of reading a book , in the process of interacting with a book, a person learns not only the past, present and future of the world, but this is the main thing. , learns to think, analyze, develops creatively; therefore, the moral and cultural foundations of his personality are formed. Moral education is a purposeful process of introducing children to the moral values of humanity and a particular society. Preschool age is an important period in a child's life, when he enters the world of social relations, learns

elementary moral requirements and learns to fulfill them. It was during this period that they formed the foundations of moral ideas, which are the most important condition for the formation of moral culture. The problem of moral education has always worried teachers. In different historical periods of society's life, the content of education came to the fore. Thus, KD Ushinsky wrote about folk art, labor and labor education, aimed at forming feelings of patriotism and love for one's people.

Introduction to the environment plays a special role in the comprehensive development of preschool children. It is appropriate to start introducing children to the world from the animal world close to them. Because the children's interest in the animal world is very high. Through this, their imagination and perception can be formed. Expanding children's imaginations about the animal world, introducing them to their useful aspects, forming a friendly relationship with animals. Getting children interested in the animal world. Formation, expansion and development of children's knowledge about the animal world. When introducing children to the animal world, dividing them into two groups (domestic and wild animals); to enrich the imagination of what animals eat and about them.

Technology of implementation of educational process: pictures with pictures of animals, figurines. : small figurines of animals, drawings. observation, oral control, self-control, question and answer. The educator uses easy and effective ways to introduce children to the animal world are taught the names of animals, and their ideas about domestic and wild animals are strengthened. Educators use new pedagogical technologies in introducing children to the animal world and improve its implementation; work on oneself; connecting the topic with life examples and events; improving pedagogical skills. During the lesson, children will learn that animals have adapted to live in different conditions. At the same time, they will have an idea that animals are divided into several groups.

References:

1. Preschool pedagogy textbook. authors FR Kadirova and others: "Tafakur Publishing House", Tashkent 2019 (685 pages)
2. O. Safaochil "The spirituality of independence and the foundations of education" Teacher Tashkent-1997 (208 pages)
3. Narzullaev O'.Kh. "Problems of the right to protect and use the animal world" Tashkent 2007 (27 pages)
4. Mirzaev Rustam " Journey to the animal world" Tashkent Zarqalam, 2004.
5. (188 pages)